

SOME ASPECTS OF LEADERSHIP IN THE CHILD AND ADOLESCENT ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract: *This article reveals the problem of leadership in children and adolescents, as well as the research of scientists on this topic in different historical periods.*

Key words: *leadership, leader, leadership qualities.*

The socio-economic changes taking place in contemporary Russian society have led to a change in moral and value priorities in the formation of personality. The ability to communicate, to think independently and freely, to find creative ways of solving different kinds of problems are valued more highly today than a large amount of information. Modern education is focused on the development of these qualities of personality, which is reflected in the Republican State Educational Standard (RGOS).

The priority task of a modern school is to

Preparing students for real life, which implies the readiness of the individual to openly express and defend his or her social position, critically assess their intentions, thoughts and actions, and take

to take responsibility for the results of their own actions, to be

purposefulness and persistence in achieving the result, to adapt in the dynamically changing and developing world, etc. [1]. Therefore, the most relevant today are the issues of forming a positive social experience of a growing person, his civil formation.

In the current political and social situation in our country, the leadership qualities of a person become very important. The stimulation of leadership is of great importance in solving the problems of the social formation of the child's personality. Schoolchildren, as a rule, occupy key positions in the bodies of student self-government [3].

Let's turn to the scientific interpretations revealing the concept of "leadership". It should be noted that this phenomenon became the object of research of many figures

of science in the first half of the XX century. At that time the most famous was the theory of leadership traits, which recognized the innateness and uniqueness of the leader's properties. That is why leadership as a socio-psychological phenomenon should be considered as a set of outstanding personality traits, guaranteeing leaders the ability to take a leading position and maintain authority due to the presence of these unique traits. At the same time, researchers note that a significant shortcoming of this theory is the position that leadership is not only a product of social conditions, relationships, and an innate complex of biopsychic properties that provide power to people who possess these qualities.

So, A.V. Petrovsky thought: "In this theory the following circumstance is not taken into account: performance of leadership functions forms or promotes formation of certain qualities in a leader; if a person performs this role for a long time, there is an interiorization (appropriation) of normative requirements of the role, and this leads to fixation of personality traits necessary for effective leadership". [4].

Until the mid-1980s, the studies concerning the phenomenon of leadership identified four groups of leadership traits: physiological, mental (intellectual), psychological, (emotional, personal) and business.

The first works in this aspect date back to the 20-30s of the last century (A.S. Makarenko, A.S. Zaluzhny, E.A. Arkin, etc.). The named authors mainly concerned mainly with the phenomenon of leadership in children's groups. And here it is necessary to address the ideas and pedagogical experience of well-known teacher A.S. Makarenko.

In his institutions (Gorky Colony and Commune named after F. Dzerzhinsky), he created conditions under which each pupil in a certain situation could take on the role of leader, and in another situation, the same pupil voluntarily became the executor, giving his fellow pupil the opportunity to show managerial skills. This is clearly visible in the system of combined units created by A.S. Makarenko in the colony named after A.M. Gorky. A.M. Gorky. As the author himself said, "The system of combined units made life in the colony very tense and full of interest, alternation of work and organizational functions, exercises in command and in subordination, collective and personal movements" [2].

Scientific research and real practice allow us to state that a leader is a member of a group who is recognized as having the right to make the most

The leader is a member of a group who has the right to make the most responsible decisions in meaningful situations, i.e. the most authoritative person who plays a central role in organizing and regulating relations in the group. A leader has the most authority and recognition in his/her group. The leader is not appointed, he or she is promoted himself or herself due to his or her personal qualities.

According to R. L. Krichevsky, every group of people, regardless of age, necessarily has a leader who will influence the other members of the group. But there is such a peculiarity that a personality, which has shown itself as a leader in one case, can yield to another leader in another case [6].

Younger school age is no exception in the manifestation of leadership qualities. The leader-child also performs leadership functions: leads the class collective, makes decisions, senses the mood of other children, participates in conflict resolution, and is responsible for his or her actions.

A characteristic feature of all leaders is usually high employment and participation in various social events [7].

The modern level and conditions of people's lives, numerous obstacles on the way to achieve their goals require from a person the skills to be purposeful, active, in other words - to be a leader. It can be concluded that a confident, energetic person with adequate self-esteem will achieve great success in life and career, and such qualities, according to V.G. Maralov and V.A. Sitarov, should be formed from a young age [5].

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